

Nucleation studies in supersaturated aqueous solutions of magnesium and zinc doped nickel sulphate heptahydrate

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Induction period has been measured for various supersaturated aqueous solutions of nickel sulphate heptahydrate doped separately with magnesium sulphate heptahydrate and zinc sulphate heptahydrate by the direct vision method. Various critical nucleation parameters have been calculated based on classical theory for homogeneous nucleation. The critical nucleation parameters decrease with the increase in concentration of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ doping but increase with the increase in concentration of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ doping in the $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solutions.

Nucleation process is the initial and most important phenomenon in liquid-solid phase transition. Based on the classical theory for homogeneous crystal nucleation certain critical nucleation parameters like interfacial tension (σ) of the solid relative to its solution, energy of formation (ΔG) of a critical nucleus, and radius of the nucleus (r) in equilibrium with its solution can be calculated using the induction period (τ) which can be measured^{1,2}.

Nickel sulphate heptahydrate (merrenosite), $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, belongs to the orthorhombic crystal system having a tetramolecular unit cell of dimensions ($a = 11.86$, $b = 12.08$ and $c = 6.81$ Å) and is isomorphous with $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Ref. 3). The crystal is green in colour. It is soluble in water and its solubility at 20° is 37.7 parts by weight per 100 parts by weight of water. The molecular weight and density are 280.88 and 1.948 gm/cc respectively⁴.

An attempt has been made in the present study to determine the nucleation parameters of pure $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and also to investigate the effect of the isomorphous substances $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as impurities added heavily (impurity concentration 2000–10000 ppm) on the nucleation parameters of these crystals. $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was doped with $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ separately each in six different $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$: dopant molecular ratios, viz. 1 : 0.0 (pure $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$), 1 : 0.002, 1 : 0.004, 1 : 0.006, 1 : 0.008 and 1 : 0.010. Induction periods were measured for various supersaturated solutions by the direct vision method. Various critical nucleation parameters have been calculated and the effect of supersaturation and concentration of doping on them is also reported and discussed.

Results and Discussion

The measured induction periods are presented in Table

1. For both the dopants, the value of τ decreases and hence the nucleation rate increases as the supersaturation and concentration of doping of the aqueous solution increase. Similar results were observed by previous authors for their systems^{2,5,6}.

Plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(S)$ (S is the supersaturation) are presented in Figs. 1 and 2. As per the classical theory

Fig. 1. Plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(S)$ for $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ doped $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(S)$ for $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ doped $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

for homogeneous crystal nucleation, it is expected to observe linear plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(S)$. In the present

Table 1. Results of induction period measurements

Doping ratio	S*	τ (s) for	
		ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O doped NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O doped NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O
Pure	1.850	5100	5100
NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1.875	3600	3600
	1.900	2700	2700
	1.925	1500	1500
	1.950	600	600
1 : 0.002	1.850	2820	3360
	1.875	2100	2880
	1.900	1440	1920
	1.925	1080	960
1 : 0.004	1.850	1620	2208
	1.875	1140	1998
	1.900	780	1422
	1.925	600	830
1 : 0.006	1.850	900	1436
	1.875	720	962
	1.900	480	550
	1.925	400	337
1 : 0.008	1.850	780	944
	1.875	660	620
	1.900	460	333
	1.925	360	153
1 : 0.010	1.850	280	50
	1.850	660	600
	1.875	540	360
	1.900	420	180
	1.925	300	55
	1.950	240	30

*Saturated concentration for NiSO₄·7H₂O = 0.937 M.

study, we have observed nearly linear plots for higher doping concentrations for both the dopants considered. Small deviation from linearity has been observed at lower supersaturation levels (of the two dopants, the deviation is less for ZnSO₄·7H₂O dopant). This deviation is highly significant for the pure system (NiSO₄·7H₂O). Also, this deviation is significant for doping ratios 1 : 0.002 and 1 : 0.004 for MgSO₄·7H₂O dopant and 1 : 0.002 for ZnSO₄·7H₂O dopant. Previous authors also observed significant non-linearity with their systems^{2,6,7}.

This non-linearity has been explained not due to the dif-

Fig. 3. Dependence of energy of formation of critical nucleus on supersaturation for ZnSO₄·7H₂O doped NiSO₄·7H₂O.

Fig. 4. Dependence of energy of formation of critical nucleus on supersaturation for MgSO₄·7H₂O doped NiSO₄·7H₂O.

ficulties in the induction period measurements but due to the heterogeneous nucleation caused by the unwanted impurity particles naturally present in the solvent⁸. Linear relationship may be expected at higher supersaturations because the effect of the natural impurity particles present in the solvent is dominated by the presence of greater amount of solute. Also, a substance with higher solubility may dominate over the unwanted natural impurities present in the solvent more effectively than a substance with lower solubility. The present study indicates that when the dopants are isomorphous to the pure system, the higher soluble dopant (ZnSO₄·7H₂O) is able to dominate over the unwanted natural impurities present in the solvent in a better way than the dopant with lower solubility (MgSO₄·7H₂O).

The effect of solvent impurities cannot be reduced by increasing the supersaturation because the maximum practical limit for the induction period measurement does not allow the supersaturation to exceed 1.950. If the supersaturation is beyond this practical limit, nucleation occurs before the attainment of supersaturation. Hence, in order to reduce the effect of these practical difficulties on the nucleation parameters the results were obtained in the present study using the slopes determined in the linear region of the line plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(S)$.

The nucleation parameters are presented in Table 2. The

Table 2. Nucleation parameters*

Doping ratio	For ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O doped NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O			For MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O doped NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		
	σ mJ m ⁻²	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	r nm	σ mJ m ⁻²	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	r nm
Pure NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	7.389	30.247	1.872	7.389	30.247	1.872
1 : 0.002	6.905	24.673	1.748	7.435	30.805	1.882
1 : 0.004	6.349	19.175	1.607	7.574	31.326	1.917
1 : 0.006	5.968	15.927	1.511	7.816	35.785	1.979
1 : 0.008	5.872	15.170	1.486	8.267	42.345	2.093
1 : 0.010	5.843	14.946	1.479	8.438	45.020	2.136

* ΔG and r values calculated at the maximum supersaturation.

values of ΔG and r at various supersaturations have also been calculated for all the crystals and the results are presented in Figs. 3–6. The values of ΔG and r decrease when the supersaturation is increased. This result is similar to that observed by previous authors for their systems. The nucleation parameters decrease with the increase in concentration of ZnSO₄·7H₂O doping and increase with the increase in concentration of MgSO₄·7H₂O doping in the NiSO₄·7H₂O solution.

Fig. 5. Dependence of radius of critical nucleus on supersaturation for ZnSO₄·7H₂O doped NiSO₄·7H₂O.

Fig. 6. Dependence of radius of critical nucleus on supersaturation for MgSO₄·7H₂O doped NiSO₄·7H₂O.

A qualitative explanation to the variation of nucleation parameters with doping concentration was attempted by considering the densities of the dopants⁶. The nucleation

parameters increase with the doping concentration for the denser dopants and decrease with the doping concentration for the rarer dopants. The dopants considered in the present study do not hold the above density rule. The densities of MgSO₄·7H₂O, NiSO₄·7H₂O and ZnSO₄·7H₂O are respectively 1.68, 1.95 and 1.96 g ml⁻¹ (Ref. 1). So, variation of nucleation parameters with the doping concentration in the present study may be understood in a different way.

As MgSO₄·7H₂O and ZnSO₄·7H₂O are isomorphous to NiSO₄·7H₂O, a qualitative explanation can be attempted by considering the lattice volumes or molecular volumes (one-fourth of the lattice volumes in the present case) of the dopants. The lattice volumes (calculated using the lattice parameters³) of MgSO₄·7H₂O, NiSO₄·7H₂O and ZnSO₄·7H₂O are respectively 983.497, 975.661 and 968.294 Å³. The nucleation parameters increase with the doping concentration for the dopant with larger lattice (MgSO₄·7H₂O) and decrease with the doping concentration for the dopant with smaller lattice (ZnSO₄·7H₂O).

Experimental

Analytical reagent grade samples of NiSO₄·7H₂O, MgSO₄·7H₂O and ZnSO₄·7H₂O and doubly distilled water were used. Aqueous solutions of various supersaturated concentrations were prepared by dissolving the required amounts of NiSO₄·7H₂O and the dopant at temperatures slightly higher than the saturation temperature. Supersaturation was obtained by natural cooling.

Induction periods were measured following the reported procedures². Experiments were performed with the five selected supersaturations, viz. 1.850, 1.875, 1.900, 1.925 and 1.950 at 32°. Volume of the solutions taken in the nucleation cell was maintained at 20 ml in all the experiments. Several nucleation runs were carried out under controlled and unstirred conditions. Reproducible results

were obtained with an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$.

The direct vision method is not very accurate and does not involve rigorous methodology to study nucleation. The nuclei are non-observable even by microscopy; at the observable level, they are already at the growth stage. It is assumed that the time required for the critical nucleus to grow to an observable level is very small compared to the induction period, and is negligible. Despite all these problems, this method was considered for the present study for the reason that no other better method was available to study nucleation in supersaturated solutions of highly soluble substances. Moreover, in order to reduce the inaccuracy, care was taken that the supersaturated concentration considered should provide the induction period of at least more than 25 s. The effect of heterogeneous nucleation by dust particles from air was reduced by carrying out the experiment in a relatively dust-free space. Also, the effect of heterogeneous nucleation by scratching on the inner wall of the nucleation cell (glass beaker) was reduced by properly choosing the glass beaker without scratches (tested with a microscope).

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